

plots A and B. Although insects and snails in plots C and D reduced production, 78-79.5 kg inocula produced more than 225 kg biomass within 16 d, fully covering the plots for the first incorporation was (see table). The second incorporation was at 30 d, when about 85 kg biomass (64 kg inoculum + about 10 kg leftover mass in plots A and B + residual mass in plots C and D) also produced about 225 kg biomass.

The 25-m² area generated adequate inocula that multiplied rapidly, to fully cover the entire field twice in 30 d. Cost was 650 g SSP, 15 g CF, and 10 g Ph. ■

Biomass production potential of azolla in a ricefield. West Bengal, India, 1990 wet season.

Parameter	Plot	4 d	8 d	12 d	16 d	20 d	24 d	28 d	30 d
Fresh biomass (kg)	A	25.3	16.1	20.5	16.3	20.0	18.2	16.5	9.3
	B	21.0	16.3	20.1	16.1	20.5	18.0	16.5	9.0
	C	-	-	-	^a	-	-	-	^a
	D	-	-	-	^a	-	-	-	^a
SE±		1.6	1.1	2.3	1.5	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.0
Insects (no./m ²)	A	x	x	5	12	x	x	x	x
	B	x	x	3	9	x	x	x	x
	C	x	3	4	19	22	5	7	7
	D	x	2	4	22	17	6	12	12
SE±			0.56	0.56	1.13	1.69	0.65	0.85	1.13
Snails (no./m ²)	A	x	x	2	2	2	x	x	9
	B	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	3
	C	6	7	5	9	9	8	10	10
	D	4	x	7	9	9	12	14	13
SE±		0.56	1.13	0.56	1.69	1.69	1.41	1.13	0.94

^aAll biomass incorporated.

Fertilizer management - inorganic sources

Plastic-coated urea (PCU) as a nitrogen source for lowland rice

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We compared the response of rice to N from a new PCU (4.5% plastic coating with 44% N) supplied by IFDC and from prilled urea (PU), urea supergranules (USG), urease-inhibited urea (UIU), neem-coated urea (NCU), and rock phosphate-coated urea (RPCU) Jun-Oct 1987 (southwest monsoon) and the residual effect in Oct-Feb 1987 (northeast monsoon) at CSRC (11° N, 77° E, 30 m altitude).

Soil was sandy clay loam, riverine alluvium deposited over laterite, containing 0.7% organic C, 120-8-68 ppm available NPK, pH 5.1, and EC 0.3 dS/m. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with five N levels (0, 37.5, 75.0, 112.5, 150 kg N/ha) in the main plots and six sources (PU, USG, UIU, NCU, PCU, and RPCU) in the subplots, with 3 replications.

PU and UIU were applied in three equal splits (basal, 20 d after transplanting [DT], and 40 DT); USG was placed at 6 DT; NCU, PCU, SCU, and RPCU were basally incorporated at planting. A uniform basal dose of 26 kg P and 25 kg K/ha was applied. Jaya was the test variety.

In the second season, Jaya was transplanted in the same field without altering the layout. A uniform 45-26-25 kg

NPK/ha was applied as PU, super-phosphate, and muriate of potash (45 kg N/ha is half the recommended N).

Responses to N rate and N sources in the first season were significant (Table 1). A fertilizer testing model (FTM) was fitted to the data on grain yield as

$$Y = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 N + \gamma_1 N^2 + \delta_2 N_2 + \eta_2 N_2^2 + \dots + \delta_T N_T + \eta_T N_T^2 + \xi$$

$\beta_1 > 0, \gamma_1 < 0$

The FTM tested whether response curves for USG, UIU, NCU, PCU, and RPCU were significantly different from response curves to urea. Regression coefficients $d_i, h_i, i = 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$, estimating parameters δ_i, η_i , and their significant levels (Table 2) represent additional effects due to a particular source over the effects of PU. An *F* test for the additional sum of squares resulting from

Table 2. Fertilizer testing model (FTM) regression coefficients (significance levels and R²).

Source	Regression coefficient ^a
PU	a : 2.61631
	b1 : 0.02124**
Additional effects of USG	C1 : -0.00009**
	d2 : 0.01519**
Additional effects of UIU	h2 : -0.00005
	d3 : 0.00446
Additional effects of NCU	h3 : -0.00004
	d4 : 0.00049
Additional effects of PCU	h4 : -0.00001
	d5 : 0.02555**
Additional effects of RPCU	h5 : -0.00013**
	d6 : 0.00016
	h6 : -0.00001
	R2 : 0.9122**

^a ** = significant at the 0.01 level.

Table 1. Influence on grain yield of level and source of nitrogen. Karamana, Trivandrum, India.

N level (kg N/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)													
	1987 wet season							1987 dry season						
	PU	USG	UIU	NCU	PCU	RPCU	Mean	PU	USG	UIU	NCU	PCU	RPCU	Mean
Control	2.1	2.1	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7
37.5	3.3	3.8	3.7	3.4	4.2	3.1	3.6	3.6	3.4	3.1	3.1	3.5	2.6	3.2
75.0	3.8	4.5	3.8	3.8	4.9	3.9	4.1	3.1	3.5	3.3	3.1	3.9	3.0	3.3
112.5	4.0	5.2	3.9	3.8	5.3	4.1	4.4	3.1	3.6	2.9	3.0	3.9	2.9	3.2
150.0	3.9	4.9	3.8	3.8	4.9	3.9	4.2	2.8	3.6	2.7	2.8	3.8	3.4	3.1
Mean	3.6	4.2	3.6	3.5	4.4	3.5	3.1	3.3	3.0	2.9	3.6	2.9		
<i>For comparing</i>							<i>LSD (0.05)</i>							
N levels (main plot)							0.2							
N sources (subplot)							0.1							
N sources at a fixed N level							0.3							
N levels at a fixed or different level							0.3							

Table 3. Mean squares and *F* test for additional sum of squares corresponding to N sources.

Source of additional sum of squares	Parameter	Mean square ^a
USG	δ2η2	0.785
UIU	δ3η3	0.015
NCU	δ4η4	0.010
PCU	δ5η5	1.175**
RPCU	δ6η6	0.005
Error	σ2	0.27
	(df)	12

^a** = significant at the 0.01 level.

including parameters δ_{η_i} = 2 to 6, in FTM is given in Table 3.

The significant regression coefficients d₅ h₅ indicate that the response curves of PCU and urea are different. The values d₅ > b₁ and h₅ = c₁ indicate that the response of rice to the N in PCU was larger than to that in PU. The effect of PCU was greater than that of all other sources tried.

Carryover effects of N on the succeeding northeast monsoon crop depended on the source of N. PCU at 112.5 kg N/ha had the most carryover effect. The least carryover effects were with RPCU, NCU, UIU, and PU.

Total grain yield for both seasons was highest with PCU at 112.5 kg N/ha in the first crop and PU at 45 kg N/ha in the second crop. ■

Effect of N source on irrigated rice yield in Cameroon

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Irrigated rice has been grown in Ndop Plain, Western Cameroon, since the early 1970s without any specific fertilizer recommendation. To fertilize their rice crops, most farmers use a 20-10-10 complex recommended for coffee.

We compared the effect on rice yield of three locally available N-fertilizer products (urea, diammonium phosphate (DAP), 20-10-10 complex) applied as basal, followed by urea or ammonium sulfate (AS) topdressed during 1987-89 wet seasons (mid-Jul to mid-Dec).

Experimental soil was Tropaquept, clay loam texture, pH 5.1, 3.08% organic C, 0.23% total N, 4.5 ppm available P (Bray 1), 39% base saturation, CEC 16.6 meq/100 g, 4.12 meq/100 g Ca, 1.63 meq/100 g Mg, and 0.67 meq/100 g K (NH₄OAc extractable). N (80 kg/ha) was

applied in three equal splits: basal, 21 d after transplanting (DT), and at panicle initiation. A common 26 kg P, 33 kg K/ha were applied as triple super-phosphate and muriate of potash. P and K rates were adjusted for the amount of P and K applied with DAP and 20-10-10. Basal fertilizers were broadcast and incorporated before transplanting rice. Fertilizer was topdressed by broadcasting in plots with 5-6 cm standing water, followed by hand stirring into the soil.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Four-wk-old seedlings of IR7167-33-2-3 were transplanted in 20-m² plots at 25 × 15-cm spacing 2 d after basal fertilizer application. The plots were continuously flooded from transplanting to the late dough stage. A 12.56-m² area in the middle of each plot, leaving two border rows on all sides, was harvested for yield measurements.

N treatments did not differ significantly in two of the three years (see table).

DAP applied basal followed by urea or ammonium sulfate topdressing gave the highest yields. ■

Effect of neem extract-coated urea on rice yield and nitrogen use efficiency of transplanted rice

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We evaluated prilled urea (PU) and neem extract-coated urea (NECU) at 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha during 1988-89 wet seasons. Urea was coated with neem extract in 100:1 ratio on weight basis. Experimental soil was a deep black Vertisol, with pH 7.7, 0.6% organic C, 25.1 kg available Olsen's P/ha, 240.7 kg available K/ha, and 0.2 ppm available Zn.

Half the PU was incorporated before transplanting and half in equal topdressings at tillering and panicle initiation. NECU was applied half before transplanting and half at tillering. All plots received 26.4 kg P, 33.2 kg K/ha. Rice variety Jaya was transplanted at 20 × 10-cm spacing, 3 seedlings/hill.

Grain yield was significantly higher with 150 kg N/ha applied as NECU in

Grain yield of irrigated rice as affected by nitrogen source. Ndop Plain, Cameroon. 1987-89 wet seasons.^a

Treatment ^b			N rate (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
Basal	Topdress 1	Topdress 2		1987	1988	1989	Mean
None	None	None	0	2.5	4.6	5.1	4.1
Urea	Urea	Urea	80	3.4	6.0	6.7	5.4
20-10-10	AS	Urea	80	3.5	5.5	6.3	5.1
20-10-10	Urea	Urea	80	3.9	5.5	5.4	4.9
DAP	AS	Urea	80	4.3	5.8	6.9	5.7
DAP	Urea	Urea	80	4.3	6.2	6.9	5.8
LSD (0.05)				1.0	0.8	0.8	
CV (%)				18.1	10.0	8.4	

^aAv of 4 replications. ^bAS = ammonium sulfate.

Influence of NECU and PU on grain yield and number of productive tillers. Kota India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Mean productive tillers (no./m ²)
	1988	1989	
Control (no N)	3.6	3.5	214.0
90 kg N/ha, PU	5.0	5.0	284.0
120 kg N/ha, PU	5.7	5.6	294.6
150 kg N/ha, PU	6.0	5.9	318.6
90 kg N/ha, NECU	5.7	5.7	292.1
120 kg N/ha, NECU	6.0	5.9	306.0
150 kg N/ha, NECU	6.3	6.3	335.9
LSD (0.05)			
	0.4	0.3	20.1